

Kinetic Study of an Oleophilic Cation Exchange Resin in Nonaqueous Media. Part-II. Effect of Sulphonation

MOSTAFA M. EMARA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science,
Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

and

NAZIK A. FARID

Petroleum Research Institute, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

Manuscript received 18 January 1984, accepted 21 July 1984

In this communication we report a kinetic investigation on a resin similar to that of Gregor's type with higher capacity. The detailed procedure of synthesis and characterisation is reported.

The kinetic results of this high capacity oleophilic cation exchange resin in the ^{22}Na isotope with ^{23}Na are discussed and compared to that of the low capacity resin published elsewhere¹⁰.

The purpose of this study in pure ethanol medium is to confirm the mechanistic behavior of the exchange process of these types of resins in pure non-aqueous medium. Also this study includes the effect of sulphonation of the resin on the rates of exchange.

REACTIONS using cation exchange resins and different kinds of bases have been reported in a variety of solvents¹⁻³. In almost all of the processes the system was not completely anhydrous. The resins were air-dried containing a certain amount of moisture. New methods were tried to synthesise the kind of resin to be used in non-aqueous solvents. The first method is mechanical macroreticular resin. Kunin and his coworkers⁴ have reported a new polymerisation technique for the preparation of the macroporous structure similar to those of conventional absorbents such as alumina. Gregor *et al.*⁵ have prepared a new class of non-aqueous swelling ion-exchange resins. Since then several publications appeared both theoretical^{7,8} and experimental⁹ development in mixed and pure non-aqueous media. In an earlier investigation¹⁰ the kinetics of an oleophilic cation exchange resin of Gregor's type of low capacity was carried out in absolute ethanol.

In this communication we report the kinetic investigation on a resin similar to that of Gregor with higher capacity and the detailed procedure of synthesis and characterisation reported.

Experimental

Materials: NaOH, potassium acetate and sodium acetate (Fisher) were anhydrous. NaCl and KCl were analytical reagent grade and 2-bromophenol was Fisher product. Sodium-22 chloride

was procured from Nucleonic Corporation of America. LSI-4 and LSI-5 were lauroylated polystyrene sulphonates with different capacities and synthesised as explained below.

Synthesis of LSI-5: The beads (Dow Chemical) having polystyrene with 1% divinyl benzene (DVB) crosslinkage, were lauroylated in our laboratory by Friedel-Craft method as used by Gregor⁶. Lauroylation was found to be 88%. The sulphonation procedure was then carried out as follows: Triethyl phosphate (100 ml) and 1,2-dichloroethane (425 ml) were mixed together with stirring for 0.5 h. 70 ml of sulfon B was then added dropwise (5 drops/min) and for the first 20 min the temperature raised from 25 to 27°. After 1 h the rate of dropping was increased up to 15 drops/min and the temperature went up to 29°. The addition of sulfon B was complete in 2.5 h while the temperature was brought down to 25° by means of cold bath. The lauroylated polystyrene beads (100 g) were then added to the above yellowish brown mixture. The temperature was then increased to 28° and within 5 min the colour of both the beads as well as the solution turned black. The temperature was dropped down to 26° within 15 min. After 2 h the solution was syphoned off. Acetone was added to the resin and left overnight after washing several times with it. Next day the solutions was syphoned off and the resin was filtered and left to dry in air (yield 148 g). The resin was then exposed to extraction by methanol for two days. The

sulphonation was found to be 80%, which is close to the theoretical value (84%). This resin was abbreviated as LSI-5. Another resin abbreviated as LSI-4 was synthesised using the same procedure with less amounts of the above mentioned material per 100 g beads to obtain 47% sulphonation. LSI-4 and LSI-5 resin characteristics are shown in Table 1. The kinetic data of LSI-4 was published in an earlier report¹⁰.

The radiotracer experiment was carried out to determine the nature of the exchange reactions in ethanol, *i.e.* the exchange is diffusion or chemically controlled.

When the experiment was carried out using the LSI-4 resin two steps, one being fast and the other slow were observed. The following assumptions were made :

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION OF LSI-4 and LSI-5

Resin	Lauroylation %	Sulphonation %	Capacity H ⁺ meq/g	Swelling H ₂ O %	Ethanol %
LSI-4	88	47	1.26	37	187
LSI-5	88	80	2.26	35	190

Analytical procedures : ²²Na—Na exchange : Sodium-22 has a half life of 2.6 years and emits gamma radiation. The activity of the various samples employing ²²Na as a tracer was measured by means of scintillation Geiger counter Chicago model 1810. The instrument was calibrated using cesium-137.

Kinetic batch experiment : In carrying out the experiment in pure ethanol media special precautions had to be taken to prevent the surrounding moisture. A glove bag of polyethylene with integral gloves provided a relatively water-free nitrogen atmosphere. The apparatus necessary for the experiment was inserted in the glove bag and then purged off residual air using dry nitrogen.

To carry out the kinetic experiment a known amount of the resin in the proper form ; ²²Na, or Na dried at 70° in vacuum over (2 mm Hg) was put in the glove bag. The resin was then transferred to a 500 ml Erlenmeyer flask (dried at 120° for 24 h, then N₂ passed through it for 1 h before use). Then absolute ethanol (165 ml) was added to the resin and shaken till the resin swelled completely in 0.5-1 h. To start the kinetic-exchange experiment, 35 ml of the proper concentrated solution in ethanol was added to make the necessary concentration after dilution to 200 ml. Aliquots were taken out at intervals with calibrated syringe, and analysed using the proper technique.

Results and Discussion

The two oleophilic cation exchange resins, LSI-4 and LSI-5 were prepared and characterised (Table 1). In this part we report the results of LSI-5 kinetics using two concentrations of sodium acetate in the bulk solution (0.022 and 0.044 M). The purpose of this study in the pure ethanol medium is to confirm the mechanistic behavior of the exchange processes of these new types of resins in the pure non-aqueous medium¹⁰. Also this study includes the effect of sulphonation of the resin on the rates of exchange.

(i) The rate controlling step is chemical exchange and not the diffusion one.

(ii) The process can be represented by the following equation.

(iii) The mole fraction of Na⁺, X_{Na} was nearly unity.

(iv) The concentration of Na⁺ and ²²Na⁺ in the bulk solution phase is identical with that within the resin pore phase or that the diffusive process is very rapid compared to the exchange reaction.

(v) k₁ = k₋₁ = k

(vi) The mole fraction of ²²Na, X²²Na in the resin is negligible compared to that of Na in the bulk solution.

We were able to obtain a rate expression¹⁰ for the above reaction in the following form :

$$\frac{da}{dt} = k(x - ya)$$

where a is activity of the radioactive ²²Na in the resin ; x and y are numerical constants, dependent on the volume and the mole fraction of ²²Na in the resin ; and t is the time.

Integrating this rate expression we obtain log (1-x'a) = -y' kt, where x' and y' are new numerical constants depending on the bulk concentration.

In the log (1-x'a) plot against time in hours, for LSI-4 resin, the curve was not a straight line. This is anticipated as we do not have a real first-order but pseudo-first order rate equation. Also it is seen that we had two separate reactions, one being relatively faster than the other. The half-life times may be calculated from the plots and the rate constants from the slopes of the plots. In each case a plot of the left hand side of the above mentioned equation vs t is drawn, and the rate constants calculated.

The two kinds of reactions are due to the difference in acidity of the sulfonic groups when the benzene rings are lauroylated or not. In LSI-4 resin there are 47% sulphonated groups, and 88% lauroylated and 12% non-lauroylated rings. If this explanation is the plausible one and the rate determining step is mainly chemical then the LSI-5 resin in which the extent of sulphonation and lauroylation is almost the same, the two types of reactions should converge to almost one.

The $^{22}\text{Na}^+ - \text{Na}$ exchange reaction was carried out using the LSI-5 resin at two sodium acetate concentrations (0.022 and 0.044 M) as shown in Table 2 and Fig. 1. We observe that the portion of

the fast reaction in the figure started to disappear, indicating that the slow step become the dominant factor due to the homogeneity of the acidity of the sulfonic groups in this resin.

Table 3 summarises the analysis using LSI-5 resin at 25°, while Table 4 includes the rate constants for both LSI-4 and LSI-5 for the two steps.

It is interesting to notice that the rate constants for LSI-5 in both the concentrations are higher by a factor of about 2 for the slow step and of 8-10 for the faster step. However, the effect of concentration on the rates of the LSI-5 resin is not too large. In conclusion, the study includes the

Fig. 1. $\text{Log}(1-xa)$ vs t for $\text{R}^{22}\text{Na}-\text{Na}$ (0.022 and 0.04) at 25° for LSI-5.

0.044 M Na-acetate		0.022 M Na-acetate	
Time h	$Q_t/Q_\infty \times 100$	Time h	$Q_t/Q_\infty \times 100$
0.166	1.0	0.166	3.2
0.332	3.6	0.332	3.8
1.0	3.1	1.0	6.0
2.0	5.6	2.0	8.0
5.0	11.0	5.0	15.1
8.0	15.7	7.0	17.4
25.0	23.2	24.0	28.5
48.4	32.5	48.0	35.0
99.0	43.0	97.4	43.4
144.0	48.9	144.0	49.7
195.0	52.5	193.0	54.4
288.0	56.5	286.5	62.1
385.0	64.4	384.0	65.4
480.0	58.1	482.5	67.3
624.0	73.0	624.0	73.1

0.022 M Na-acetate		0.044 M Na-acetate	
Time h	a cpm	Time h	a cpm
0.166	32	0.166	11
0.332	39	0.332	39
1.0	61	1.0	34
2.0	83	2.0	62
5.0	157	5.0	123
7.0	181	8.0	176
24.0	299	25.0	261
48.0	368	48.4	367
97.4	459	99.0	489
144.0	527	144.0	559
193.0	581	195.0	603
286.5	668	288.0	653
384.0	706	385.0	748
482.5	729	480.0	679
624.0	797	624.0	857

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS (κ) OF ²²Na—Na EXCHANGE REACTION

Resin	Na mol dm ⁻³	k	
		Slow	Fast
LSI-4*	0.012	6.04 × 10 ⁻⁴	8.5 × 10 ⁻³
LSI-4*	0.024	7.50 × 10 ⁻⁴	12.0 × 10 ⁻³
LSI-5**	0.022	1.10 × 10 ⁻³	8.7 × 10 ⁻²
LSI-5**	0.044	1.30 × 10 ⁻³	9.0 × 10 ⁻²

*Ref. 10.

**This work.

synthesis of a new class of resin which can be used in non-aqueous media. The kinetics of exchange for the two resins of the same structure but different % sulphonation and the same % of lauroylation has also been observed. A new mathematical model

has been developed¹⁰, assuming that the rate determining step in this solvent is chemical rather than diffusion.

References

1. G. W. BODAMER and R. JUMIN, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1953, **45**, 2577.
2. S. WILSON and L. LAPIDUS, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1956, **48**, 992.
3. Y. KORKISCH and F. TERA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1960, **15**, 177.
4. G. E. JANAUER and J. KORKISCH, *Talanta*, 1961, **8**, 569.
5. R. KUNIN, B. MATZNER, and N. BORTAICK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 305.
6. A. G. TSUK and H. P. GREGOR, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 5538.
7. H. D. SHARMA, R. E. JERVIS and L. W. McMILLEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 969.
8. R. KUNIN and R. L. GUSTAFSON, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1969, **61**, 38.
9. C. W. EINOLF, JR. and E. L. CARSTENSEN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 1091.
10. M. M. EMARA, *Pak. J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1980, **23**, 97.